

In-plane anisotropic optical and mechanical properties of two-dimensional MoO₃

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Abstract: Molybdenum trioxide (MoO₃) in-plane anisotropy has increasingly attracted the attention of the scientific community in the last few years. Many of the observed in-plane anisotropic properties stem from the anisotropic refractive index and elastic constants of the material but a comprehensive analysis of these fundamental properties is still lacking. Here we employ Raman and micro-reflectance measurements, using polarized light, to determine the angular dependence of the refractive index of thin MoO₃ flakes and we study the directional dependence of the MoO₃ Young's modulus using the buckling metrology method. We found that MoO₃ displays one of the largest in-plane anisotropic mechanical properties reported for 2D materials so far.

Keywords: MoO₃, complex oxides, anisotropy, phonon polaritons, flexible electronics, Angle-resolved polarized Raman spectroscopy, Young's Modulus

Introduction

Recently, two-dimensional (2D) materials with an in-plane anisotropy, such as several transition metal chalcogenides, group-VA and VV compounds or black phosphorus, have been

extensively studied¹⁻²¹. Some of them have demonstrated a great potential in optoelectronics and flexible electronics applications²²⁻²⁵, allowing the fabrication of devices with new functionalities (e.g. polarization sensitive photodetectors^{22,26}) and observing novel quasi one-dimensional physics²⁷. Molybdenum trioxide has a relatively low direct bandgap ($>2.7\text{eV}$)²⁸, useful for gas sensor²⁹ and resistive memory technology³⁰, optoelectronic³¹⁻⁴⁰, electrochromic⁴¹ and flexible^{42,43} applications. The difference between the in-plane (*a-c*) lattice parameters makes α -MoO₃ a perfect candidate to investigate optical, mechanical, and electrical in-plane anisotropic properties. Indeed, calculations show that in-plane carrier mobility exhibit strong anisotropic behavior⁴⁴ and highly anisotropic propagation of phonon polaritons have been recently observed in α -MoO₃⁴⁵⁻⁴⁸. In comparison with metallic plasmon polaritons, phonon polaritons can achieve reduced optical losses, improved light confinements and higher quality factors⁴⁹⁻⁵². The origin of the preceding properties is mainly due to the anisotropy of the fundamental properties of molybdenum trioxide, that have been scarcely investigated.

Here, we have studied the direction-dependent refractive index (birefringence) and Young's Modulus of α -MoO₃ exfoliated flakes, properties which govern the anisotropy observed in Raman and phonon polariton experiments, through a combination of experiments and density functional theory calculations. We studied thin flakes of α -MoO₃ deposited on SiO₂/Si substrates and identified the crystallographic orientation of samples using angle-resolved polarized Raman spectroscopy technique⁵³. Then, we determined the in-plane anisotropy of the MoO₃ refractive index using angle-resolved polarized micro-reflectance spectroscopy, finding a remarkably large birefringence. The anisotropic mechanical properties of the MoO₃ flakes was experimentally investigated with the buckling metrology method^{54,55}, finding one of the largest Young's modulus anisotropy reported so far for 2D materials.

Results and Discussion

We have grown MoO₃ flakes in atmospheric conditions using a modified version of the hot plate-based physical vapor transport method described in Ref. ⁵⁶. Briefly, a molybdenum foil was oxidized on a hotplate at 540°C, then a silicon wafer was placed on top. At this temperature, the molybdenum oxide sublimates and re-crystallizes on the surface of the Si wafer, which is at a slightly lower temperature, forming MoO₃ flakes. Then, a Gel-Film (Gel-Pak WF x4 6.0 mil) stamp is used to pick-up and exfoliate the MoO₃ flakes. These flakes can be then transferred onto a 297 nm SiO₂/Si substrate using deterministic transfer set up (see Materials and Methods section for more information).

Figure 1a shows the layered crystal structure of α -MoO₃⁵⁷⁻⁵⁹, belonging to the *Pbnm* space group. It consists of a double-layer stacking of linked distorted MoO₆ octahedra in the *b* direction, along which the adjacent layers are linked by weak van der Waals forces, while in-plane atoms are strongly bonded. This configuration leads to lattice parameters: $a = 3.96 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 13.86 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 3.70 \text{ \AA}$ (JCPDS file: 05-0508)^{44,53,56,59,60}.

We have used angle-resolved polarized Raman spectroscopy technique to identify the different crystal directions in our MoO₃ flakes. Using a linearly polarized laser in a Raman system (see Materials and Methods section) and setting the analyzer and polarizer in a parallel configuration, while we rotate the sample, we obtain the spectra shown in Fig. 1b. The system set up is depicted in Fig. S1 in the Supplementary Information and it is explained in detail by Liu, X. et. al⁶¹. Typical MoO₃ Raman modes are A_g and B_g⁶² and it has not found any correlation between the Raman modes and the MoO₃ thickness⁶³. We highlight the peaks centered at 282 cm⁻¹, assigned to B_{2g} mode, and at 156 and 818 cm⁻¹, assigned to A_g^c and A_g^a mode, respectively. The A_g^c peak corresponds to the translation vibration of the rigid MoO₆ octahedra chains along the *c*-axis, and the A_g^a mode is the asymmetric stretching vibration of O-Mo-O atoms along the *a*-axis^{53,62}.

We have carried out angle-resolved polarized Raman measurements in a MoO₃ flake of 28 nm of thickness from 0° to 360°, with a step of 4°. The thickness has been determined by combination of atomic force microscopy with recently developed optical microscopy based

techniques⁶⁴. In Fig. 1b three of these measurements at different angles (0°, 45° and 90°) are displayed. Notice the difference in intensity of each mode, revealing how the relative orientation between the polarization angle and the direction of the crystalline axes plays an important role in the Raman process. In fact, previous works have shown how the A_g and B_{2g} mode intensities can be fitted to:^{53,62}

$$I(A_g) \propto (A \cos^2 \beta + C \sin^2 \beta)^2 \quad (1)$$

$$I(B_{2g}) \propto E^2 \sin^2 2\beta \quad (2)$$

where β is the relative angle between the a -axis crystal direction and the linear polarization direction of the laser. Figure 1c shows the normalized intensity angle-resolved polarized Raman measurements of each mode (light red), with the resulting fit to equations (1) and (2) (in dark red), showing an excellent agreement. Note, the A_g^c and A_g^a modes are useful to extract the crystal structure of the sample due to their 180-degree periodicity. The inset in Figure 1b shows a microscopy image of the MoO_3 flake on SiO_2/Si , studied with the Raman spectroscopy. The c - and a -axes, determined from the Raman measurements are depicted in the figure and coincide with the straight edges produced during the exfoliation of the MoO_3 flake.

Fig. 1 (a) Crystal structure of MoO₃ in *Pbnm* notation, spheres in blue (red) represent Mo (O) atoms, the two different views belong to *ca* (top), and *ba* plane projection (bottom). (b) Raman spectra at 0° (blue), 45° (black) and 90° (red) angles with respect to the horizontal axis. A_g^c, B_{2g} and A_g^a Raman modes are highlighted with vertical dashed lines. Inset: Microscopy image of the sample placed in the initial position (0°) and the *c* and *a* axes, determined from the angle-resolved Raman measurements, are shown. (c) Polar plots, in light red; and fittings, in dark red, of angle-resolved normalized Raman intensities of the A_g^c (left), B_{2g} (middle) and A_g^a (right) modes.

In order to gain an insight about the in-plane anisotropic optical properties of MoO₃ flakes we carried out micro-reflectance measurements employing linearly polarized incident light. Figure 2 shows the optical contrast spectra acquired for different alignment between the crystal axis and the incident linear polarization (see the bottom inset). The optical contrast *C* is defined as:

$$C = \frac{I_{fl} - I_{sub}}{I_{fl} + I_{sub}} \quad (3)$$

where I_{fl} and I_{sub} are the intensity measured on the MoO₃ flake and on the bare substrate, respectively. Interestingly, it has been demonstrated how one can use a simple Fresnel law-based model to accurately reproduce the measured optical contrast spectra⁶⁴. Moreover, given the known refractive indexes of air, SiO₂ and Si and the known thickness of the SiO₂ film and MoO₃ flake one can determine the refractive index of the MoO₃ flake for different alignment between the incident linearly polarized light and the crystal directions by using the refractive index as a fitting parameter to achieve the best fit of the Fresnel law-based model to the experimental data. The top inset in Figure 2 shows the resulting in-plane angular dependence of the refractive index displaying a marked anisotropy (birefringence). While along the a-axis the refractive index of MoO₃ is $n_a = 2.21 + 0i$, along the c-axis the refractive index increases up to $n_c = 2.30 + 0i$. The difference Δn between n_c and n_a , is ~ 0.1 . This value is comparable that of well-known strongly birefringent materials like calcite (-0.17) and barium borate (-0.12).^{65,66} If we compare it with other anisotropic 2D materials, the birefringence of MoO₃ is larger than that of ReS₂ and ReSe₂ (~ 0.04)⁶ but substantially lower than the values reported for black phosphorus (0.25)⁶ or TiS₃ (0.3)⁶⁷. However, note that, unlike MoO₃, all these anisotropic 2D materials are rather opaque in the visible range of the electromagnetic spectrum, limiting their application in polarization optics applications. Therefore, the birefringence value of MoO₃, although more modest in comparison with TiS₃ or black phosphorus, can have a stronger impact in future ultrathin polarization optics applications. These experimental results for MoO₃ are confirmed by theoretical ab-initio calculations through the solution of the Bethe-Salpeter's equation, in which we have obtained refractive index values of $n_a=2.40$ and $n_c=2.60$ at small frequency, with a difference $\Delta n \sim 0.2$. We find these theoretical values close to the ones obtained experimentally. We attribute the lower birefringence experimental value to the presence of defects in the MoO₃ flakes, not considered in the calculations, that can effectively reduce the anisotropy of the lattice.

Fig. 2 Optical contrast vs. wavelength as function of the angle of the flake from 0° to 90° of the MoO₃ of a 28 nm of thickness flake shown, which is horizontally oriented along the *a*-axis. Inset: Polar plot of the change in refractive index as a function of the relative orientation between the incident linearly polarized light and the *a*-axis of the crystal.

In the following we focus on the characterization of the anisotropy of the Young's modulus, one of the fundamental magnitudes that govern the mechanical properties of materials, of MoO₃ flakes. We use buckling induced metrology method, which has been proved to be an easy, but reliable way to study the Young's modulus of thin films^{54,55} and 2D materials⁶⁸⁻⁷². The method relies on studying the buckling instability that arises when a thin film is deposited onto an adhesive compliant substrate, and it is subjected to uniaxial compression⁷³. Because of this compression, there is a trade-off between the adhesion forces between film and substrate and the bending rigidity of the film leads to a rippling pattern of the thin film, which is characteristic of the film and substrate properties (in the Supplementary Information can be found an animated GIF, Supplementary GIF, of a α -MoO₃ flake compressed in this way). The wavelength, λ , of the rippling pattern can be used to determine the Young's modulus:

$$E_f = 3 \left(\frac{\lambda}{2\pi h} \right)^3 \frac{1 - \nu_{fa} \nu_{fc}}{1 - \nu_s^2} E_s \quad (4)$$

being h the flake thickness, ν_s , ν_f , E_s and E_f the Poisson's ratio and Young's Modulus of substrate and flake, respectively. The Poisson's ratio of α -MoO₃ must be taken along the two axes. Using density functional theory (more details available in the Supplementary Information) we calculate Poisson's ratios of α -MoO₃ correspond to $\nu_{fa}=0.147$ and $\nu_{fc}=0.06$. In our experiment we used a Gel-Film substrate as compliant substrate, with $\nu_{sub}=0.5$ ⁷⁴ and its Young's Modulus is $E_{sub}=492 \pm 11$ kPa⁶⁸.

Figure 3a shows optical images of a 24 nm thickness MoO₃ flake (thickness and orientation obtained with optical microscopy based technique, shown in Figure S2) when it is subjected to compression along the c- and a-axes. Upon compression along different orientations the MoO₃ develops a rippled pattern whose periodicity depends on the direction. In Fig. 3b, a statistical study with 14 different samples with thicknesses ranging from 18 to 62 nm (white circles), from which we obtain the mean Young's Modulus values and their standard deviation along the a- and c-axis. We use histograms to show the flake-to-flake variability of these results and we fit them with a normalized Gaussian distribution function. Moreover, we plot the corresponding two-dimensional normalized Gaussian distribution function in a 2D gray colormap, in which the density of datapoints is associated with the colorbar, set as inset. The obtained Young's modulus values along the a- and c-axes directions are $E_{a-axis} = 44 \pm 8$ GPa and $E_{c-axis} = 86 \pm 15$ GPa, respectively. Interestingly the anisotropy ratio (E_{c-axis}/E_{a-axis}) is ~ 2 among the largest value reported in the literature for anisotropic 2D materials: black phosphorus ~ 2.7 ,¹⁷ for orpiment (As₂S₃) is ~ 1.7 .⁷⁵ Our DFT calculations predict even higher Young's modulus values (91.9 GPa and 216.9 GPa for the a- and c-axis respectively) in relatively good agreement with the values reported for bulk-like MoO₃ (~ 200 nm thick) crystals through Brillouin scattering. Note that the presence of defects in the synthesized MoO₃ samples could explain the lower Young's modulus values obtained in our experiments.

Fig. 3 (a) Optical images of a MoO₃ flake on Gel-Film substrate applying compression along *a* and *c* axes (top images), inset: process of ripples formation; determination of the wavelength of periodic ripples (bottom figure). (b) Scatter density plot of Young's modulus values along the two directions obtained from 14 different samples, white circles with black edges, and fitted with a multivariate Gaussian normal distribution function, in gray. Inset: Histogram plots of Young's modulus along the *a*-axis (blue) and the *c*-axis (red), fitted with a Gaussian distribution.

Conclusions

In summary, we combined Raman spectroscopy, micro-reflectance and buckling metrology to probe the anisotropic optical and mechanical properties of exfoliated MoO₃ flakes. We found that the flakes show a strong birefringence, i.e. their refractive index depends on the alignment between the polarization of the incident light and the crystalline axis. The difference between the refractive index for light polarized along the *c*- and *a*-axes reaches ~ 0.1 . This large value, together with the fact that MoO₃ is transparent in the visible range, makes this material a good candidate for future polarization optics applications. Regarding the mechanical properties, we found that the experimental Young's modulus along the *a*- and *c*-axes directions are $E_{a\text{-axis}} = 44 \pm 8$ GPa and $E_{c\text{-axis}} = 86 \pm 15$ GPa, respectively, yielding an anisotropy ratio of ~ 2 , only overpassed by black phosphorus. Our results agree with ab-initio calculations of optical and elastic properties of MoO₃. The anisotropy in the refractive index and the Young's modulus have strong impact in many optical and mechanical properties and thus, we believe that our work can

be used as the foundation of further works studying the intriguing anisotropic properties of MoO₃.

Methods

Growth and Deposition

We have based our present grown procedure on a modification of the hot plate growth method developed by Molina-Mendoza et. al⁵⁶.

Once the growth of the crystals is finished, the MoO₃ flakes are firstly exfoliated onto a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) (Gel-Film WF x4 6.0mil, by Gelpak®) and then transferred onto a 297 nm SiO₂/Si substrate using a deterministic transfer method^{76,77}.

Optical Microscopy and Spectroscopy

Optical microscopy images were acquired using a Motic BA310 MET-T microscope equipped with a 50× 0.55 NA objective and an AMScope MU1803 CMOS Camera. Reflection spectra were collected from a spot of ~1.5–2 μm diameter with a Thorlabs CCS200/M fiber-coupled spectrometer (Thorlabs Inc., Newton, New Jersey, United States). More details about the micro-reflectance setup can be found in Reference ⁷⁸.

Raman Spectroscopy

Raman characterization of MoO₃ flakes on 297 nm SiO₂/Si substrates were carried out with a confocal Raman microscopy system (MonoVista CRS+ from Spectroscopy & Imaging GmbH) using a 532 nm excitation laser with an incident power of 1.234 mW and a 100× objective with the integration time of 20 s.

Numerical methods

We have analyzed the optical and elastic properties of MoO₃ using the YAMBO and Quantum Espresso suite of programs^{79–81}. For the electronic structure calculation we have used the generalized gradient approximation in the PBE parametrization for the exchange-correlation

energy with a plane wave cut-off of 60 Ry⁸². The electronic structure calculations are performed on a Monkhorst-Pack grid of 8x8x8 points. We have chosen norm-conserving pseudo potentials in the SG15 database⁸³.

For the elastic properties, we have used the thermo_pw code from the Quantum Espresso suite⁸⁴. The elastic properties agree when we used either norm-conserving or ultra-soft pseudo potentials.

Data Availability

Data presented in this study are available on request from the authors.

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Author Contributions

S.P. fabricated the MoO₃ flake samples and performed the experimental work. R.F, C.M. and A.C.-G. supervised and designed the experiments. S.P., C.M. and A.C.-G. drafted the firsts version of the manuscript. R. D'A. developed the theoretical calculations. All authors contributed to writing the final version of the manuscript.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.